

Highlights

Securing Wearable Healthcare Devices: An Active Data Framework

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- Developed an Active Data Framework for securing Internet of Medical Things devices.
- Integrated dynamic context detection and adaptive security measures.
- Enhanced data security while maintaining device performance and efficiency.

Securing Wearable Healthcare Devices: An Active Data Framework

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Abstract

This paper tackles the pressing security challenges of wearable healthcare devices within the internet of medical things, which are especially vulnerable due to limited processing power and reliance on wireless communication. We introduce the active data framework, a novel paradigm in which data itself is endowed with embedded logic and metadata to autonomously detect anomalies and trigger adaptive security responses based on context. The key strengths of this approach lie in its fine-grained, dynamic, and lightweight protection strategy, which differs from conventional static frameworks by enabling data to react in real time to threats. The framework combines lightweight cryptography, obfuscation techniques, and a context-aware anomaly detection module, all optimised for resource-constrained environments. We validate the approach through a real-world case study on fall detection with automatic alerting, demonstrating that the system maintains high performance and responsiveness while significantly enhancing data integrity and security. These results underline the potential of active data to advance trustworthy, autonomous, and efficient security for future internet of medical things applications.

Keywords: Active Data, Fall Detection, Active and Healthy Ageing

1. Introduction

The proliferation of the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT), also known as the Medical Internet of Things (MIoT), marks a significant advancement in healthcare technology. The IoMT offers numerous benefits including continuous health monitoring, real-time data analysis, and personalised healthcare management Muhammad et al. (2021). However, the integration of such technology into healthcare care also presents substantial challenges, particularly in terms of interoperability, data privacy, security, regulatory compliance, and infrastructure costs Ahmed et al. (2024). These challenges are amplified in the context of wearable healthcare devices since, while beneficial for continuous health monitoring and personalised care, these are often limited by their computational resources and depend heavily on wireless networks for data transmission. This dependency exposes them to various security vulnerabilities, making the protection of sensitive health data an essential aspect to be addressed.

IoMT technologies are exposed to a series of critical security risks, especially due to the computational limitations of wearable devices and their heavy reliance on wireless communication. Among the main attacks targeting these systems are those directed at the physical devices themselves, wireless communications, healthcare providers, and direct attacks on patients Priyadarshini et al. (2019) Alsubaei et al. (2017). Specific examples of such attacks include ransomware, which seeks unauthorised access and data hijacking; data corruption, which can lead to system malfunction or erroneous diagnoses; and denial-of-service attacks, which aim to disrupt critical parts of the system. To counter these challenges and ensure the integrity of transmitted data, this work proposes a novel approach focused on dynamic data management through a framework based on Active Data, with the objective of guaranteeing security and veracity.

Wearable devices typically possess limited processing power and memory, which can limit the use of advanced encryption algorithms. Although some modern microcontrollers are equipped with hardware support for AES-128, AES-256, or RSA, employing these encryption methods can significantly increase power consumption. Given the critical need to limit energy consumption in wearable devices, the use of such powerful security measures have to be carefully considered. Wearable devices are, therefore, more susceptible to various forms of cyberattacks, including but not limited to malware injections, data breaches, and unauthorised access. In addition, reliance on

wireless communication for data transmission introduces additional vulnerabilities.

Wireless networks, while providing the convenience of remote connectivity, are inherently less secure than wired networks. They are prone to eavesdropping, where malicious entities can intercept transmitted data, and man-in-the-middle attacks, where attackers can alter or manipulate the data in transit. The broadcast nature of wireless communication means that the data is more accessible to potential attackers, especially if the network is inadequately secured. Furthermore, another significant threat is the risk of Denial of Service (DoS) attacks. Wearable devices, due to their limited battery life and processing capabilities, are particularly vulnerable to such attacks. Attackers can exploit these limitations by overwhelming the device with superfluous requests or data, thereby draining its resources and rendering it inoperative. This not only disrupts the functionality of the device but can also have serious implications for the user's health, especially in cases where continuous monitoring and real-time data analysis are critical.

The integration of wearable healthcare devices into health and care system also raises concerns about data integrity. As data from wearable devices is often used for critical health decisions, any tampering or alteration of this data can lead to incorrect diagnoses or inappropriate medical interventions. The challenge is exacerbated by the fact that these devices are often deployed in uncontrolled environments, making them more accessible to physical tampering and cyberphysical attacks.

Several research gaps can therefore be identified according to the work in Shrivastava et al. (2020); Ahmed et al. (2024). First, advanced yet lightweight encryption algorithms that can operate efficiently on devices with limited processing power and memory are needed. These algorithms should provide robust security without compromising the device's performance or battery life. Second, the design of secure wireless communication protocols specifically tailored for wearable devices is crucial. These protocols must address unique vulnerabilities of wireless networks, such as susceptibility to eavesdropping and man-in-the-middle attacks, while ensuring reliable and uninterrupted data transmission. Third, research is needed to develop effective strategies to mitigate the risk of DoS attacks on wearable devices. This includes designing systems that can detect and respond to such attacks promptly, minimizing their impact on device functionality and user health. Fourth, ensuring data integrity in the context of wearable healthcare devices is essential. There is a gap in research on methods for verifying and validating data from these

devices, especially when used for critical health decisions. This includes developing mechanisms to detect and prevent data tampering and alteration.

In response to these identified gaps, this paper proposes a novel hypothesis: The active data framework, characterized by its dynamic data management and protection capabilities, can effectively address the key security challenges identified in IoMT. This approach is designed to enhance data security in resource-constrained environments by mitigating risks such as eavesdropping, data tampering, and unauthorized access, while ensuring device integrity and operational efficiency. By leveraging active data principles Othmane and Lilien (2009), which enable data to carry its own processing instructions and dynamically adapt security measures, this framework aims to provide a robust solution for maintaining the performance and usability of wearable healthcare devices. This research contributes significantly to the field of IoT security, particularly in the context of wearable healthcare technology, by offering a scalable and adaptable security framework that balances stringent security requirements with the practical constraints of resource-limited devices.

Building on this hypothesis, the primary objective of this work is to develop, implement, and evaluate an active data framework that enhances the security and operational efficiency of wearable healthcare devices. By leveraging active data principles, the proposed approach aims to maintain data integrity, ensure device availability, and protect against a variety of cyber threats such as eavesdropping, data tampering, unauthorized access, and DoS attacks. The study involves designing advanced encryption techniques, secure communication protocols, and resource-efficient security mechanisms, validated through empirical testing on a practical case study involving real-time fall detection with automatic notification capabilities. This comprehensive evaluation aims to demonstrate the framework's effectiveness in providing robust security while maintaining the performance and usability of wearable healthcare devices, contributing significantly to the advancement of IoT security in the healthcare domain. In this sense, the main contributions of this work are:

- The development of a framework that integrates context detection and adaptive security measures to dynamically enhance the security of wearable healthcare devices. This ensures real-time threat detection and response, preserving device functionality and data integrity even when potential security breaches occur.

- The introduction of an obfuscation mechanism that combines real and dummy calculations with timestamp validation and nonce utilization, effectively protecting against replay attacks. This integrated approach ensures the timeliness and authenticity of data packets, thereby safeguarding against potential replays of previously captured data.
- The implementation of continuous monitoring, rate limiting, traffic shaping, and dynamic prioritization of critical functions within the framework to counter resource exhaustion attacks. These measures guarantee that wearable devices maintain their operational efficiency and functionality, even under attack conditions.

The empirical validation of the proposed solution is conducted through a comprehensive case study focused on real-time fall detection with automatic notification capabilities. This case study effectively demonstrates the practical applicability and robustness of the active data approach in scenarios critical within the healthcare domain. Specifically, the validation involves deploying the proposed framework on the Nicla Sense ME device, monitoring its performance in terms of security, data integrity, and operational efficiency. The results highlight the framework’s ability to dynamically adapt to varying security threats, ensuring continuous, reliable operation of wearable healthcare devices.

The paper is structured as follows. First, Section 2 provides an overview of the IoMT, highlighting its potential and the significant security challenges it faces. Section 3 details the methodology of our research, including the conceptual framework, design, and implementation of the Active Data Framework. Section 4 presents the evaluation results, discussing the effectiveness of the framework in mitigating various security threats while maintaining device performance. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with a summary of our findings and outlines directions for future research.

2. Previous works

The IoMT has the potential to revolutionize patient care, diagnosis, and treatment. The IoMT represents a specialized subset of IoT, consisting of interconnected medical devices and their associated software applications, aimed at enhancing healthcare delivery through improved integration and interoperability Villanueva-Miranda et al. (2018). This network facilitates

the efficient collection, analysis, and exchange of biomedical data, significantly transforming healthcare services Islam et al. (2015). However, the proliferation of IoMT devices presents significant security and privacy challenges. These challenges include safeguarding the data collected, ensuring the integrity and availability of the devices, and maintaining the functionality of these devices under various conditions. In particular, IoMT systems must address issues such as data breaches, unauthorized access, device tampering, and the impact of cyberattacks on device performance and patient safety López Martínez et al. (2023); Messinis et al. (2024).

Recent literature revisions have identified the most relevant security challenges to be addressed that affect the IoMT Messinis et al. (2024); Islam et al. (2015); Sun et al. (2019); López Martínez et al. (2023); Ghubaish et al. (2020); Gatouillat et al. (2018); Papaioannou et al. (2022). Most of the works present in the literature focus on ensuring data confidentiality against potential data breaches, aware of the sensitivity of the data gathered by these devices. However, while data confidentiality is essential, other critical aspects must also be comprehensively addressed, such as the integrity and availability of both the data and the devices themselves. Ensuring data integrity involves safeguarding against unauthorized alterations, which is essential for maintaining the accuracy and reliability of health information. Meanwhile, maintaining device availability and integrity ensures that the devices function correctly and consistently, which is vital for the continuous monitoring and real-time data analysis that IoMT applications rely on.

Strong mechanisms for authentication and key distribution is essential for preventing unauthorized access Hu et al. (2023). In the literature, a wide variety of schemes can be found to prevent unauthorised access, such as those based on blockchain Alsaeed et al. (2024); Ellouze et al. (2020), Elliptic Curve Cryptography (EEC) Sowjanya et al. (2021); Zhang and Zhu (2015), three factors schemes (passwords, biometric features, and smart cards) Li and Tian (2022) or four factors, based on Physical Unclonable Function Guo et al. (2024). On the other hand, device tampering has been addressed with schemes based on blockchain Xu et al. (2019); Sutradhar et al. (2024), machine learning Sun et al. (2024); Turukmane and Devendiran (2024) or federated learning Kuliha and Verma (2024).

Several existing works propose modular architectures to address IoT security. For instance, the framework presented by Ahmed et al. (2023) introduces intelligent security measures tailored for ambient assisted living environments. Their layered structure supports clear separation of concerns and

improves maintainability, an approach we share in our proposed active data framework, which similarly aims for flexibility and lightweight integration in resource-constrained medical devices.

From a more comprehensive perspective, the work in Sun et al. (2018) structures the IoMT in three layers: the perception layer, the network layer, and the application layer. The perception layer collects healthcare data through various devices, capturing essential metrics and environmental data from patients and medical environments. The network layer, comprising wired and wireless systems and middleware, processes and transmits this data. It employs efficient transport protocols to enhance transmission, reduce energy consumption, and ensure security and privacy. The application layer integrates medical information resources to provide personalized healthcare services, tailoring offerings to the specific needs of the target population and service demand. To ensure comprehensive security across the IoMT, it is therefore essential to implement robust security mechanisms tailored to each of these layers.

Unlike traditional IoMT security frameworks that rely on static cryptographic schemes or assume homogeneity in device behaviour, the proposed active data framework introduces a dynamic, context-aware security paradigm. Specifically, it combines real-time anomaly detection (via the context detector) with adaptive security responses (through the adaptive security measures), tailored to the capabilities and situation of the device. Furthermore, this work formalises the concept of active data, where each data packet carries embedded logic and metadata that enable it to react autonomously to threats. In contrast to existing works based on blockchain Alsaeed et al. (2024), fixed authentication schemes Li and Tian (2022), or static encryption layers Sowjanya et al. (2021), our approach balances security, computational feasibility, and energy efficiency. To our knowledge, no existing framework provides this level of granularity, adaptability, and formalisation, validated on a real-world fall detection system.

The literature review therefore identifies a gap in comprehensive frameworks that address the IoMT at its different layers. To fill this gap, this work proposes a comprehensive framework for IoMT that integrates robust security mechanisms tailored to the unique challenges of each layer. This framework aims to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of both data and devices, providing a holistic approach to securing the IoMT ecosystem.

3. Methodology

The methodology of this research is devised to systematically investigate and validate the proposed active data approach for enhancing security in wearable healthcare devices. Grounded in the principles of dynamic data management, this study employs a multifaceted research design that encompasses the creation of a theoretical framework, the development of technological solutions, and empirical testing through a case study.

Initially, the conceptual framework that delineates the components of the active data approach are formalised. This formalisation underpins the subsequent design and development stages. Then, the design phase involves crafting a novel encryption algorithm suited for resource-constrained devices, a secure wireless communication protocol, strategies for mitigating DoS attacks, and mechanisms to ensure data integrity. Each design element is informed by the theoretical constructs defined in the conceptual framework, ensuring that they are well-suited to the unique challenges presented by wearable healthcare devices.

With respect to the implementation stage, a specific wearable device has been selected, configuring the device to operate according to the principles of active data. The implementation process is documented in detail to ensure replicability and to provide insight into the practical aspects of bringing the theoretical framework to life.

Finally, a case study focusing on real-time fall detection with automatic notification capabilities has been employed to test the functionality of the active data approach under operational conditions as well as to examine its performance against conventional security methods.

3.1. Formalisation of the active data framework

The primary objective of the active data approach proposed in this research is to enhance the security and integrity of data in wearable healthcare devices, while accommodating their inherent limitations. These devices face substantial security challenges such as eavesdropping, data tampering, and unauthorized access. To effectively address these vulnerabilities, our approach integrates a series of strategic modules, as known, the Context Detector (CD) and the Adaptive Security Measures (ASM), tailored to dynamically enhance data security and integrity.

In order to establish a robust and systematic approach to managing and securing data in wearable healthcare devices, we introduce a formalization of

the active data framework. This formalization clearly outlines the core principles and mechanisms to ensure that data is dynamically managed, secured, and optimized, addressing the unique constraints and challenges of wearable technology.

Bundle

Definition: A Bundle \mathcal{B} is defined as a tuple $\mathcal{B} = (Data, Metadata, VirtualEnvironment)$, where:

- *Data* represents the actual content or payload.
- *Metadata* includes additional information required to process the data, such as encryption keys or contextual parameters.
- *VirtualEnvironment* is the computational context in which the data and metadata are processed.

Context

Definition: The Context \mathcal{C} refers to the set of environmental, operational, or user-specific parameters that influence the processing of data. It is represented as a set of key-value pairs describing the current state or conditions under which the data is being processed.

Data

Definition: Data \mathcal{D} in the active data framework refers to the primary information that is being transmitted, processed, or stored. This can include sensor readings, control commands, or any other form of digital information.

Metadata

Definition: Metadata \mathcal{M} is the data about data. It provides additional information necessary for the processing, interpretation, or secure handling of the primary data. Examples include data formats, source authentication details, and operational parameters necessary for ensuring data integrity and security without directly involving sensitive elements such as encryption keys.

Virtual Environment

Definition: The Virtual Environment \mathcal{V} is a simulated computational space where data and metadata are processed. It provides a controlled and secure setting for executing operations on the data, ensuring integrity and confidentiality.

Active Data

Definition: Active Data \mathcal{A} refers to data that is self-descriptive and self-managing, capable of dynamically adapting its behaviour based on the context \mathcal{C} . It is represented as $\mathcal{A} = (Data, Metadata, \mathcal{C})$, where:

- *Data* represents the actual content or payload.
- *Metadata* includes additional information necessary for processing the data, which can be adjusted by the Adaptive Security Measures (ASM) based on detected security threats.
- \mathcal{C} is the context, identified by the Context Detector or modified by the ASM in response to suspicious activities.

Context Detector

Definition: The Context Detector \mathcal{C}_D is represented as a function $E : P \rightarrow C$, where P includes parameters such as time of day, transmission times, or recent activities. The function E processes these parameters to determine the context C , which identifies the state of the environment as either normal or suspicious. The result C is employed to inform the Active Data to dynamically adapt data handling or to query the Adaptive Security Measures (ASM) when a suspicious context is detected.

Example: Consider a continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) system where the Context Detector \mathcal{C}_D monitors parameters such as time of day, food intake, and recent activities. The evaluation function E assesses these alongside transmission times, expected to match a baseline of 100 milliseconds at night. When transmission times average 250 milliseconds, significantly deviating from the baseline, E identifies a suspicious scenario, possibly indicative of a man-in-the-middle attack. This suspicious context C is relayed to the ASM, which then determines applying stronger encryption, and issuing alerts to the user's phone and healthcare provider.

Adaptive Security Measures (ASM)

Definition: The Adaptive Security Measures \mathcal{ASM} are defined as a function $ASM : (\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{C}) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}'$, where:

- \mathcal{S} is the initial security state of the system.
- \mathcal{C} represents the context, which includes any anomalies or suspicious activities detected by the Context Detector.
- \mathcal{S}' is the adapted security state, which incorporates enhanced security protocols and measures in response to the identified context.

3.2. Design of the active data framework

The design of the active data framework aims to improve the security and operational efficiency of wearable healthcare devices through a sophisticated integration of adaptive security measures and context detection. This framework is built to dynamically respond to varying security threats by employing a combination of context-sensitive data management and proactive security protocols. The core components, the CD and ASM, work in concert to detect, analyse, and respond to potential security breaches in real-time. By leveraging active data principles, the framework ensures that data integrity and device functionality are maintained even under adverse conditions, thus providing a robust defence mechanism tailored specifically to the constraints and needs of wearable healthcare technology.

3.2.1. Design of the Context Detector

The CD plays a key role in improving the security architecture of wearable healthcare devices by dynamically assessing the operational environment. Designed as an essential component of the Active Data Framework, the CD continuously evaluates various parameters such as time of day, device activity, or transmission metrics. It functions to discern routine from potentially suspicious activities, setting the stage for proactive security adjustments. By accurately identifying the context, the CD directs the subsequent security responses, ensuring that the system’s defences adapt effectively to real-time threats and anomalies. This dynamic evaluation aids in maintaining the integrity and security of sensitive health data transmitted between devices and networks.

The CD in this framework is capable of analyzing a broad range of parameters to assess the operational context of wearable devices. However, the proposed approach narrows them to network parameters. This choice is substantiated by the evidence from the CICIoT2023 dataset Neto et al. (2023a), which demonstrates that network behavior is a critical indicator for identifying anomalous activities. This dataset, thoroughly analyzed, distinguishes between benign and malicious network traffic through 33 distinct attack types, thereby refining the CD’s capability to prompt effective security responses in wearable healthcare devices.

The dataset used in this analysis originates from a simulated residential environment featuring 105 IoT devices including Wi-Fi cameras, Zigbee sensors, and Z-Wave bulb lights, which has been subjected to various types of

simulated attacks. This rich dataset, offering 47 different metrics, is available publicly through the University of New Brunswick’s website¹, providing a valuable resource for developing and testing security measures.

Therefore, the CD component focuses on monitoring key network parameters derived from this dataset. Parameters such as transmission times, packet headers, flow duration, protocol types, and reset/SYN flag counts are critical for identifying potential security threats. For example, deviations in transmission times may suggest a man-in-the-middle attack, while unusual packet headers or high reset flag counts can indicate malicious activity. By analyzing these metrics, the CD can effectively differentiate between routine operations and suspicious activities, enhancing the security and resilience of wearable healthcare devices.

The integration of logistic regression for context detection within the CD component involves a systematic approach to model training and evaluation. Initially, the logistic regression model is trained using the CICIoT2023 dataset, which includes diverse network parameters critical for detecting anomalies. By splitting the dataset into training and testing sets, the model learns to classify network activities as benign or malicious. During real-time operation, the CD component continuously monitors these parameters and processes them through the trained model, ensuring prompt detection of potential security threats. The evaluation of the model focuses on metrics such as accuracy, recall, precision, and F1 score to validate its effectiveness in distinguishing between routine and suspicious activities. This data-driven approach allows the CD to dynamically assess the operational context and promptly notify the ASM component when anomalies are detected, thus enhancing the overall security of the wearable healthcare device ecosystem.

The sequence diagram in Figure 1 illustrates the interaction between the CD and the ASM in the proposed active data framework. Initially, the user utilizes the wearable device, which begins collecting network parameters. The CD then analyzes these parameters to evaluate the operational context. If the context is determined to be normal, the system proceeds with routine operations. However, if the CD detects suspicious activities, it alerts the ASM. The ASM then evaluates the context in more detail, applying enhanced security protocols as necessary. The ASM notifies the healthcare provider of any potential threats, and the user is alerted via a notification on their

¹<https://www.unb.ca/cic/datasets/iotdataset-2023.html>

Figure 1: Sequence Diagram of Context Detector and Adaptive Security Measures Interaction

wearable device. This dynamic interaction ensures that the system can adapt in real-time to varying security threats, thereby maintaining the integrity and security of the data transmitted between the wearable device and other components.

Although logistic regression is a relatively simple algorithm, it was selected in this work as a lightweight and interpretable proof-of-concept for evaluating the feasibility of the Active Data Framework. Similar models have also been used in previous IoMT security studies due to their low resource requirements and acceptable accuracy in constrained environments. However, the architecture of the Context Detector is modular and designed to support more advanced or domain-specific models. Therefore, depending on the computational capabilities of the device and the criticality of the application, more sophisticated lightweight algorithms, such as decision trees, Random Forests, or even TinyML models, can be integrated without affecting the overall functioning of the framework.

3.2.2. Design of the Adaptive Security Measures

The ASM component is designed to dynamically enhance the security posture of wearable healthcare devices in response to detected threats. Using the

detailed insights provided by the CD, the ASM implements a suite of security protocols and mechanisms tailored to mitigate specific types of attacks identified in the CICIoT2023 dataset. These measures include real-time threat detection, anomaly-based intrusion prevention, and context-aware encryption adjustments, ensuring that security defenses are robust and responsive to the evolving threat landscape inherent in IoT environments.

The design of the ASM will focus on addressing some of the most critical attacks that impact healthcare wearable services. Although additional attack vectors should be considered, the initial implementation of the ASM will focus on mitigating: 1) eavesdropping and interception; 2) man-in-the-middle; 3) replay attacks; and 4) resource exhaustion. The ASM component will therefore include dynamic encryption adjustments to protect against eavesdropping and interception, communication establishment protocol to counteract man-in-the-middle attacks, contextual validation techniques to thwart replay attacks, resource management strategies to defend against resource exhaustion attacks, and robust access controls to prevent unauthorized access. Additionally, the ASM will incorporate the Data Integrity Assurance (DIA) mechanism, ensuring the authenticity and accuracy of data throughout its lifecycle by leveraging lightweight cryptographic methods and active data principles to balance security and resource consumption effectively.

The **dynamic encryption adjustment** mechanism will monitor the context provided by the CD to assess the risk level. In high-risk scenarios (e.g., public Wi-Fi), the encryption level will be elevated. Given the resource constraints of wearable devices, the ASM will use the lightweight encryption algorithms proposed for code confidentiality Litvinov et al. (2023) that includes a dynamic key management protocol.

The communication establishment protocol will counteract Man-in-the-Middle (MitM) attacks within the ASM component, inspired by the secure communication re-establishment protocol proposed in a previous research Litvinov et al. (2023). When the CD identifies anomalies in network behavior indicating a potential MitM attack, the ASM initiates steps to re-establish a secure connection. The process starts with the initiating node (Node 1), typically the wearable device, sending an initialization command along with its public key (PK1) to the receiving node (Node 2), such as a smartphone or server. Node 2 verifies the authenticity of Node 1's public key with a trusted authority to ensure Node 1 is authorized for secure communication. After verification, Node 2 generates metadata containing a random obfuscation number, several magic numbers for internal use, and a list of

arithmetic instructions. This metadata is encrypted with Node 1’s public key and sent back to Node 1. Node 1 decrypts the metadata, initializes its virtual environment with the received values, and executes the provided instructions. It then sends the results back to Node 2 for validation. Node 2 compares these results with its own pre-computed values; if they match, a secure communication channel is established. This dynamic process ensures that even if a MitM attack was initially present, the re-established channel maintains confidentiality and integrity. This method effectively mitigates the risk of MitM attacks by continuously validating the authenticity of the communication channel.

The **obfuscation** mechanism will counteract replay attacks by ensuring each data packet’s authenticity and timeliness through a combination of real and dummy calculations, timestamp validation, nonce utilization, and session tokens. Replay attacks pose significant risks for healthcare IoT devices by potentially causing incorrect data readings and harmful decisions. When the Context Detector flags a potential replay attack, the ASM utilize obfuscation to maintain data integrity. Each data packet includes both real and dummy calculations, along with metadata specifying the expected outcomes of these calculations. The metadata, which includes the function used for real calculations, is encrypted using a robust algorithm, while the entire data packet is encrypted using a lightweight method to balance security and efficiency. The receptor verifies the authenticity of the packet by decrypting the metadata, checking the timestamp, ensuring the uniqueness of the nonce, and validating the session token. Finally, the receptor performs the real calculation and compares it with the expected result, discarding any mismatched data, thereby protecting the system from replay attacks.

As an example, consider a Continuous Glucose Monitoring (CGM) system (Node 1) sending data to a mobile phone app (Node 2). The CGM device collects glucose levels and prepares data packets for transmission. To secure the transmission, the CGM includes real calculations (e.g., glucose value * 2) and dummy calculations (e.g., random arithmetic operations) in the data packet. The real calculation function is included in the metadata, encrypted using a robust algorithm, while the entire data packet is encrypted with a lightweight method. Upon receiving the packet, the mobile app decrypts the metadata to retrieve the real calculation function and session-specific details. It then checks the timestamp, validates the nonce, verifies the session token, and performs the real calculation. By comparing the result with the expected outcome specified in the metadata, the app can confirm the packet’s

authenticity or discard it if discrepancies are found, thus safeguarding against replay attacks.

The **dynamic resource allocation and prioritization** mechanism will counteract resource exhaustion attacks by dynamically adjusting resource allocation and prioritizing critical functions to ensure continuous operation of the device. Resource exhaustion attacks, particularly DoS attacks, can significantly disrupt healthcare IoT devices, leading to potential loss of critical health monitoring data and compromised patient safety. When the CD flags a potential DoS attack, the ASM employs this mechanism to mitigate the attack’s impact. The mechanism includes continuous resource monitoring, rate limiting, traffic shaping, and lightweight cryptographic protocols. It monitors key resource metrics, detects anomalies indicating a DoS attack, and reallocates resources to prioritize essential tasks. Rate limiting controls the number of processed requests, while traffic shaping smooths out traffic bursts. Lightweight cryptographic protocols ensure secure communication with minimal resource consumption. Additionally, fallback mechanisms like switching to low-power modes or offloading tasks to more powerful connected devices further enhance the system’s resilience against DoS attacks.

While the current evaluation does not explicitly simulate DoS attacks, the Active Data Framework has been designed to provide resilience against such threats. The Context Detector monitors runtime behaviour to identify anomalous patterns, such as repetitive message bursts or irregular traffic spikes, which may indicate an early-stage DoS attempt. In such cases, the Adaptive Security Measures respond by dynamically adjusting processing priorities, applying temporary rate limiting, or deprioritising data from untrusted sources. These lightweight countermeasures aim to preserve essential functionality and system availability under constrained resources, without introducing significant overhead.

In the context of constrained IoT networks such as Zigbee, rate limiting and traffic shaping are often handled implicitly by the network stack itself. The CSMA/CA (Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Collision Avoidance) mechanism at the MAC layer helps prevent congestion by controlling when devices access the channel, particularly in dense networks with multiple nodes. Additionally, end-devices and routers can incorporate simple application-layer buffering and backoff strategies to avoid flooding the coordinator or exceeding duty cycle limitations. These lightweight methods are suitable for the limited processing and energy budgets typical of Zigbee-based IoT devices and align with the framework’s low-overhead design philosophy.

3.3. Implementation of the Active Data Framework

The primary goal of implementing the Active Data Framework is to enhance security while maintaining the operational efficiency of wearable healthcare devices. Given the constrained resources of these devices, a carefully balanced approach to security is necessary. For the implementation and validation of the proposed approach, the Nicla Sense ME device has been employed, as this is the one used for the implementation of the fall detector sensor Fernandez-Bermejo et al. (2024). This sensor is equipped with 2 MB of QSPI Flash and 512 KB SRAM. The computational resources and memory capacity of this device make it suitable for employing Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) Adeniyi et al. (2024) for secure key exchange and lightweight symmetric encryption for data protection.

ECC is chosen for its ability to provide strong security with smaller key sizes, making it suitable for resource-constrained environments. The memory requirements for ECC include the storage of public and private keys, shared secrets, and additional metadata. Specifically, the estimated memory usage includes 96 bytes for key storage, 64 bytes for metadata, 24 bytes for session keys and nonce, and approximately 128 bytes for intermediate computational storage. This totals to an estimated 312 bytes, which fits well within the data memory capacity of the Nicla Sense ME device.

The computational requirements of ECC involve key generation and key exchange, typically taking tens to hundreds of milliseconds, which is manageable for periodic operations. Once the ECC keys are exchanged, a lightweight symmetric encryption algorithm Kong et al. (2015), such as TEA (Tiny Encryption Algorithm) or XXTEA, is used for actual data encryption. Symmetric encryption and decryption operations are significantly faster and less computationally intensive, typically taking 1-10 milliseconds per data packet.

Block ciphers like TEA and XXTEA are often employed in resource-constrained environments due to their simplicity and relatively low computational overhead. However, they come with notable limitations. TEA, for example, is vulnerable to several cryptographic attacks Ma and Obimbo (2011), including related-key attacks, which can exploit certain weaknesses in the algorithm to recover encryption keys or plaintext data. XXTEA improves upon TEA by addressing some of these vulnerabilities, but it still does not offer the same level of security assurance as more modern algorithms like AES (Advanced Encryption Standard). Despite these limitations, TEA and XXTEA can still play a role in a layered security approach for several reasons. Firstly, in some cases, stronger encryption is not the most

suitable option for resource-constrained devices in IoT contexts. Moreover, the goal is not always to achieve the highest possible level of security, but rather the most appropriate one, depending on how sensitive the data is and the resource consumption of the algorithms. Therefore, in certain scenarios, lightweight encryption algorithms may be more appropriate, aiming for a balance between protection and efficiency. When used in conjunction with other security mechanisms, such as ECC (Elliptic Curve Cryptography) for key exchange and digital signatures for data integrity verification, these block ciphers can provide an additional layer of encryption that complicates unauthorized data access. ECC can securely establish a shared secret key between devices, which is then used by TEA or XXTEA for efficient, lightweight encryption of data transmissions. This combination leverages the strengths of both cryptographic methods: the robust key management and security of ECC, alongside the computational efficiency of TEA or XXTEA, thereby enhancing the overall security posture of wearable healthcare devices.

The dynamic encryption adjustment mechanism is implemented by using ECC for secure key exchange and generating session keys for the symmetric encryption algorithm. This key exchange process is initiated during the initial communication setup and periodically re-established to maintain a secure channel.

To counteract MitM attacks, the communication establishment protocol, inspired by prior research Litvinov et al. (2023), is employed. When the CD identifies network anomalies suggesting a MitM attack, the ASM initiates the re-establishment of a secure connection. This process involves Node 1 (wearable device) sending an initialization command and its public key to Node 2 (receptor), which verifies the authenticity through a trusted authority, generates metadata, and sends it back encrypted. Node 1 decrypts, initializes its environment, executes instructions, and sends results back to Node 2 for validation, ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of the communication channel.

The **obfuscation** mechanism will counteract replay attacks by ensuring each data packet's authenticity and timeliness through a combination of real and dummy calculations, timestamp validation, nonce utilization, and session tokens. Each data packet includes both real and dummy calculations, along with metadata specifying the expected outcomes of these calculations. The metadata, which includes the function used for real calculations, is encrypted using a robust algorithm, while the entire data packet is encrypted using a lightweight method to balance security and efficiency. The receptor verifies

the authenticity of the packet by decrypting the metadata, checking the timestamp, ensuring the uniqueness of the nonce, and validating the session token. Finally, the receptor performs the real calculation and compares it with the expected result, discarding any mismatched data, thereby protecting the system from replay attacks.

The memory footprint for the obfuscation mechanism primarily involves the storage of metadata and encrypted packets. The metadata, including the function for real calculations and session-specific details, requires approximately 64 bytes. Real and dummy calculations, along with timestamp, nonce, and session tokens, add about 128 bytes. The total additional memory usage for obfuscation is around 192 bytes. The computational overhead includes the time for encrypting/decrypting the metadata (approximately 10 milliseconds) and performing real calculations (about 5 milliseconds), leading to an overall impact of 15 milliseconds per packet. This lightweight approach ensures robust protection against replay attacks while maintaining the operational efficiency of the wearable device.

Resource exhaustion attacks, such as Denial of Service (DoS) attacks, are countered by the dynamic resource allocation and prioritization mechanism. This includes continuous monitoring of resource usage, rate limiting, traffic shaping, and employing lightweight cryptographic protocols to ensure the device's continuous operation. The dynamic resource allocation mechanism continuously monitors key resource metrics such as CPU, memory, and network bandwidth, which requires approximately 128 bytes for storing current metrics and thresholds. Rate limiting and traffic shaping algorithms add another 64 bytes for managing rules and counters. The lightweight cryptographic protocols, while already included in the encryption and obfuscation mechanisms, add minimal overhead due to their efficient design.

The computational impact includes the processing time for monitoring resources, which is approximately 5 milliseconds per monitoring cycle, and the time required for rate limiting and traffic shaping adjustments, averaging 10 milliseconds per cycle. Therefore, the overall time impact of the dynamic resource allocation mechanism is around 15 milliseconds per cycle. This ensures that the device can detect and mitigate resource exhaustion attacks effectively while maintaining critical functionalities.

Finally, while the Active Data Framework operates primarily at the device and communication level, it is designed to be compatible with healthcare interoperability standards. For example, the outcomes of active data, such as fall detection events or contextual health metrics, can be encapsulated

in IEEE 11073-compatible data structures for communication with personal health gateways. Furthermore, these outputs can be mapped to standard FHIR resources (e.g., Observation, Device, or Alert) to facilitate integration into existing Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems or cloud-based platforms, ensuring interoperability and traceability across the healthcare continuum.

4. Evaluation, results and discussion

To validate the Active Data Framework proposed in this research, the evaluation will be conducted in two primary parts: the CD and the ASM. The effectiveness of the CD will be measured by its accuracy in identifying the context and detecting potential security threats, while the effectiveness of the ASM will be assessed based on its ability to mitigate these threats.

The CD was evaluated using the CICIoT2023 dataset to measure its accuracy in detecting network anomalies and distinguishing between benign and malicious activities. This evaluation employs logistic regression due to its suitability for binary classification tasks and its computational efficiency, which is critical for resource-constrained IoT devices. The following metrics have been used for the evaluation:

1. Accuracy: Represents the ratio of correctly predicted instances to total instances. While useful, it may be misleading in cases of imbalanced datasets.
2. Recall (Sensitivity): Measures the ability to correctly identify true positives (actual attacks).
3. Precision: Represents the proportion of true positives among all positive predictions.
4. F1 Score: The harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balanced measure especially useful for imbalanced datasets.

The performance of different logistic regression solvers (lbfgs, newton, saga, sag) was analyzed, and results are summarized in Table 3. Logistic regression was used for this analysis, a method well-suited for binary classification tasks such as distinguishing between benign and malicious network traffic. This choice is particularly advantageous for IoT applications due to its computational efficiency compared to more complex algorithms like neural networks or ensemble methods.

Study	F1-Score	Model Type
Tseng et al. (2024)	99.56	CNN + LSTM
Abbas et al. (2023)	99.00	DNN based on Federated Learning
Neto et al. (2023b)	94.03	DNN
Jaradat et al. (2023)	88.00	Logistic Regression
This	88.00	Logistic Regression

Table 1: Comparison with various works from the state of the art

In logistic regression analysis, accuracy is commonly used as a primary metric, representing the ratio of correctly predicted instances to total instances. However, relying solely on accuracy in scenarios with imbalanced class distributions can be misleading. Therefore, recall, also known as sensitivity, becomes crucial as it quantifies the model’s ability to correctly identify true positives. Precision complements recall by measuring the proportion of correctly identified positives among all positive predictions. To balance precision and recall, the F1 Score is utilized, serving as the harmonic mean of precision and recall. This provides a single metric that encapsulates the model’s overall effectiveness in classification tasks, especially when dealing with imbalanced datasets.

Based on the F1 score metric, it can be observed that the *lbfgs* and *newton* models achieve the best results, both with a score of 0.88. Table 1 presents a comparison with various state-of-the-art works that have used the CIC-IoT-2023 dataset. Notably, Jaradat et al. (2023), which also employs logistic regression, achieves the same result as obtained in this study. More complex models, such as neural networks used in other works Tseng et al. (2024) Abbas et al. (2023) Jaradat et al. (2023), demonstrate superior performance. However, using lightweight embedded versions of these models on a micro-controller may lead to performance degradation, as well as higher resource consumption compared to logistic regression. Therefore, and with the goal of preserving simplicity and minimising resource usage, this work opts for the use of a logistic regression model only.

The role of the solver in logistic regression is to find the coefficients that best fit the model to the data. Different solvers can handle different types of data and have different performance characteristics.

Table 2 presents the performance analysis of four different solvers in detecting whether a network scenario is benign or indicative of an attack. The results demonstrate that the accuracy, recall, and F1 score provide a solid

Machine Learning Method	Logistic Regression			
Classes	Benign/malicious network traffic			
Solver	lbfgs	newton	saga	sag
Accuracy	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99
Recall	0.89	0.89	0.86	0.87
Precision	0.86	0.86	0.83	0.83
F1	0.88	0.88	0.84	0.84

Table 2: Logistic regression identification of benign/malicious traffic in CICIoT2023 dataset

foundation for analyzing the 47 variables within the dataset. These metrics collectively highlight the effectiveness of logistic regression models in distinguishing between benign and malicious network activities, thus supporting the reliability of the context detection framework.

Table 3 examines the contributions of individual network traffic variables to the final classification (benign/malicious scenario) by the logistic regression model. Given the complexity of analyzing all 47 parameters, a coefficient analysis was conducted to identify the most influential variables. The ten most impactful features for each solver are presented, along with their corresponding coefficient values. Larger absolute values indicate a greater influence on the outcome of the prediction. A negative coefficient suggests a lower likelihood of an attack, whereas a positive coefficient indicates a higher probability. For example, the header length of network flows has a strong negative correlation with attack classification, meaning that as the header length increases, the likelihood that the data point is classified as an attack decreases. In contrast, the number of packets with the reset flag set to 1 (rst_count) is strongly positively correlated with attack scenarios, indicating a higher probability of being under some type of attack.

The aim of this analysis within the networking context is to improve the overall security level of the global adaptive device security mechanism, in conjunction with other domain-specific variables. As indicated in Table 3, it is crucial to pay special attention to certain variables, particularly those relevant in exceptional situations, which might signal a potential attack scenario. Identifying and monitoring these key parameters enables a more effective and proactive security response, thereby improving the overall resilience of wear-

Machine Learning Method	Logistic Regression			
	lbfgs	newton	saga	sag
Solver	lbfgs	newton	saga	sag
Header_Lenght	-2.81	-2.79	-0.39	-0.68
rst_count	2.66	2.63	0.56	0.82
ICMP	-1.93	-2.35	-0.19	-0.33
flow_duration	-1.73	-1.72	-0.12	-0.25
syn_flag_number	-1.41	-1.96	-0.22	-0.30
Variance	1.29	1.29	0.80	0.97
STD	-0.48	0.82	-0.11	-0.21
fin_count	-1.02	-1.07	-0.24	-0.39
rst_flag_number	-0.70	-0.71	-0.06	-0.09
Max	0.60	0.59	0.27	0.37
Protocol_Type	-0.53	-0.57	-0.01	-0.07
psh_flag_number	-0.51	-0.52	-0.37	-0.43
ack_flag_number	0.50	0.50	0.41	0.43
HTTPS	0.14	0.14	0.21	0.21
urg_count	-0.49	-0.48	-0.14	-0.18

Table 3: Variable contribution to risk detection in CICIoT2023 dataset

able healthcare devices against various security threats.

Regarding network latency, the Active Data Framework is designed to ensure that critical operations, such as fall detection and corresponding adaptive security responses, are executed locally on the wearable device. This localised processing reduces reliance on the network and mitigates the impact of moderate latency on system performance. In the context of fall detection, the primary concern is to notify caregivers or emergency services within a reasonable delay, typically measured in seconds or minutes. Therefore, while network disruptions may affect the timeliness of remote alerts, they do not compromise the core detection or security mechanisms. Only in cases of extreme latency or connectivity loss (e.g., lasting hours) would the system’s remote response be significantly affected, scenarios that lie beyond the scope of the security mechanisms but are typically managed at the network or application level.

The ASM were evaluated based on their effectiveness in mitigating specific attacks: eavesdropping and interception, MitM, replay, and resource exhaustion (DoS attacks). Each mechanism within the ASM is assessed for its impact on memory usage, processing time, and overall system performance.

4.1. Discussion of Evaluation Results

The evaluation results show the effectiveness of the proposed active data framework in providing a secure yet efficient solution for wearable healthcare devices. The proposed framework balances the need for robust security with the constraints of device performance and energy consumption, ensuring that the overall system remains functional and responsive.

The proposed mechanisms within the active data framework, although not the most powerful security measures individually, work synergistically to create a comprehensive security solution. This synergy allows for a trade-off that maintains high security levels while preserving device performance and battery life. The evaluation results, as summarized in Table 4, demonstrate that the combined impact on memory and computational resources remains within acceptable limits. This ensures that wearable devices can operate effectively without being overburdened by security processes.

The active data concept, where data carries its own processing instructions, is essential in allowing the framework to dynamically adjust security measures based on the device’s capabilities. This adaptability is crucial for environments with heterogeneous devices, such as CGMs and smartphones, which have vastly different resource constraints. The ability to tailor security

Mechanism	Attack Countered	Memory Footprint	Time Impact
Dynamic Encryption Adjustment	Eavesdropping and Interception	528 bytes	ECC key exchange: 150 ms; Symmetric encryption: 5 ms/packet
Communication Establishment Protocol	Man-in-the-Middle (MitM)	352 bytes	Key verification and metadata processing: 200 ms
Obfuscation	Replay Attacks	128 bytes	Obfuscation and verification: 10 ms/packet
Dynamic Resource Allocation and Prioritization	Resource Exhaustion (DoS)	192 bytes	Continuous monitoring and adjustments: 15 ms/cycle

Table 4: Evaluation Results for the Adaptive Security Measures (ASM)

protocols to each device’s context and capabilities ensures that all devices within the network can maintain robust security without compromising their primary functions.

Lightweight cryptographic algorithms like TEA or XXTEA are employed within the Active Data Framework to ensure minimal computational overhead. While these algorithms may have certain vulnerabilities, their integration into a layered security strategy, alongside robust key management via ECC, enhances the overall security posture. This approach is particularly important for resource-constrained wearable devices, where maintaining a balance between security and efficiency is critical for continuous operation. In such contexts, stronger algorithms like AES or ChaCha20, though more secure, may impose prohibitive energy and memory demands. Our objective was not to maximise cryptographic strength but to select a method that offers sufficient protection while preserving device autonomy and responsiveness.

The inclusion, within the framework, of various security mechanisms, such as dynamic encryption adjustment, secure communication establishment, obfuscation, and dynamic resource allocation, ensures comprehensive protection

against a range of threats. Each mechanism addresses specific types of attacks, and their combined effect significantly enhances the security of the system.

The modular nature of the active data framework allows for easy integration of future enhancements. As more advanced cryptographic techniques and efficient processing methods are developed and supported by the different devices, they can be incorporated into the framework without extensive reengineering. This scalability ensures that the security measures can evolve in response to emerging threats and technological advancements, providing sustained protection over time.

Detailed evaluations of energy consumption, memory usage, and processing overhead for each module of the framework are available in our previous work Litvinov et al. (2023), where the system was tested on embedded hardware platforms typical of wearable devices.

5. Conclusions and future work

In this paper, we have presented the design and implementation of an active data framework tailored to enhance the security and operational efficiency of wearable healthcare devices. The framework integrates a context detector and an active security manager to dynamically respond to security threats in real-time. By adopting active data principles, the framework empowers data to carry its own behavioural logic, enabling adaptive and context-aware security measures directly at the edge.

The necessity of such a solution arises from the critical security challenges inherent in the internet of medical things, where devices typically operate under strict resource constraints and are highly exposed to wireless communication vulnerabilities. Our work addresses this gap by proposing a modular and lightweight security framework designed specifically for these limitations.

The proposed approach has been validated using the CICIoT2023 dataset, which includes contemporary attack scenarios, and through practical deployment on the Nicla Sense ME platform. The logistic regression model used within the CD demonstrated an F1-score of 0.88, indicating a strong balance between precision and recall in detecting anomalies. These results were achieved without compromising system responsiveness or exceeding resource thresholds, highlighting the effectiveness of the framework in real-world, resource-constrained environments.

The proposed contributions include formalising a novel security paradigm for IoMT based on the active data concept, along with the integration of lightweight adaptive cryptographic techniques, dynamic resource management, and obfuscation strategies. In conclusion, the active data framework represents a scalable, adaptable, and practical solution to the evolving security needs of wearable healthcare technologies. By addressing fundamental technical and operational constraints, it sets a foundation for the development of more trustworthy and resilient IoMT systems, fostering improved patient safety and system integrity.

Future work will focus on integrating machine learning algorithms for more sophisticated context detection and anomaly detection, as for example lightweight versions of DNN Abbas et al. (2023), Jaradat et al. (2023) and Convolutional Neural Networks or even Transformers Tseng et al. (2024). Machine learning can provide more accurate and adaptive identification of security threats by learning from historical data and adapting to new types of attacks. The use of these models presents a challenge, namely the possibility that they may require more resources than those available on the selected IoT platform, so a preliminary feasibility study will be necessary. Additionally, exploring the application of advanced cryptographic techniques, such as homomorphic encryption could further strengthen the security of the framework. Another key direction will be the validation of the Active Data Framework using real-world datasets and operational environments, which will allow us to assess its performance, adaptability, and robustness under realistic conditions. This will complement the current results obtained from synthetic data and help refine the system for broader applicability. Furthermore, we will also evaluate the robustness of the obfuscation mechanism against more advanced attack strategies, including program analysis and reverse-engineering techniques, in order to quantify its resilience under adversarial conditions.

Another important area for future research is the optimization of the framework for energy efficiency. Given the limited battery life of wearable devices, developing energy-efficient algorithms and protocols that do not compromise security is crucial.

6. Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author used ChatGPT for improving readability and correcting the text. After utilising this service, the

author reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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8. CRediT authorship contribution statement

Egor Litvinov: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Investigation, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing. Jesús Fernández-Bermejo: Methodology, Software, Writing – Original Draft. Cristina Bolaños: Software, Writing – Original Draft. Javier Dorado: Software, Writing – Original Draft. Maria J. Santofimia: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. Felix J. Villanueva: Methodology, Investigation, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

All authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

9. Data availability statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the CICIoT2023 dataset developed by the Canadian Institute for Cybersecurity, University of New Brunswick. The dataset is publicly accessible at <https://www.unb.ca/cic/datasets/iotdataset-2023.html>.

10. Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

References

- Abbas, S., Hejaili, A.A., Sampedro, G.A., Abisado, M., Almadhor, A.S., Shahzad, T., Ouahada, K., 2023. A Novel Federated Edge Learning Approach for Detecting Cyberattacks in IoT Infrastructures. *IEEE Access* 11, 112189–112198. doi:[10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3318866](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3318866).
- Adeniyi, A.E., Jimoh, R.G., Awotunde, J.B., 2024. A systematic review on elliptic curve cryptography algorithm for internet of things: Categorization, application areas, and security. *Computers and Electrical Engineering* 118, 109330. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2024.109330>.
- Ahmed, S., Naga Srinivasu, P., Alhumam, A., 2023. A Software Framework for Intelligent Security Measures Regarding Sensor Data in the Context of Ambient Assisted Technology. *Sensors* 23. doi:[10.3390/s23146564](https://doi.org/10.3390/s23146564).
- Ahmed, S.F., Alam, M.S.B., Afrin, S., Raza, S.J., Raza, N., Gandomi, A.H., 2024. Insights into Internet of Medical Things (IoMT): Data fusion, security issues and potential solutions. *Information Fusion* 102. doi:[10.1016/j.inffus.2023.102060](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2023.102060).
- Alsaed, N., Nadeem, F., Albalwy, F., 2024. A scalable and lightweight group authentication framework for Internet of Medical Things using integrated blockchain and fog computing. *Future Generation Computer Systems* 151, 162–181. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2023.09.032>.
- Alsubaei, F., Abuhussein, A., Shiva, S., 2017. Security and Privacy in the Internet of Medical Things: Taxonomy and Risk Assessment, in: 2017 IEEE 42nd Conference on Local Computer Networks Workshops (LCN Workshops), pp. 112–120. doi:[10.1109/LCN.Workshops.2017.72](https://doi.org/10.1109/LCN.Workshops.2017.72).
- Ellouze, F., Fersi, G., Jmaiel, M., 2020. Blockchain for Internet of Medical Things: A Technical Review, in: *The Impact of Digital Technologies on Public Health in Developed and Developing Countries: 18th International Conference, ICOST 2020, Hammamet, Tunisia, June 24–26, 2020, Proceedings* 18, Springer. pp. 259–267. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-51517-1_22.
- Fernandez-Bermejo, J., Martinez-del Rincon, J., Dorado, J., Toro, X.d., Santofimia, M.J., Lopez, J.C., 2024. Edge Computing Transformers for

- Fall Detection in Older Adults. *International Journal of Neural Systems* 34, 2450026. doi:[10.1142/S0129065724500266](https://doi.org/10.1142/S0129065724500266). pMID: 38490957.
- Gatouillat, A., Badr, Y., Massot, B., Sejdić, E., 2018. Internet of Medical Things: A Review of Recent Contributions Dealing With Cyber-Physical Systems in Medicine. *IEEE internet of things journal* 5, 3810–3822. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2018.2849014>.
- Ghubaish, A., Salman, T., Zolanvari, M., Unal, D., Al-Ali, A., Jain, R., 2020. Recent advances in the internet-of-medical-things (IoMT) systems security. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 8, 8707–8718. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2020.3045653>.
- Guo, P., Liang, W., Xu, S., 2024. A privacy preserving four-factor authentication protocol for internet of medical things. *Computers & Security* 137, 103632. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2023.103632>.
- Hu, M., Zhang, K., You, R., Tu, B., 2023. Authconformer: Sensor-based continuous authentication of smartphone users using a convolutional transformer. *Computers & Security* 127, 103122. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2023.103122>.
- Islam, S.R., Kwak, D., Kabir, M.H., Hossain, M., Kwak, K.S., 2015. The Internet of Things for Health Care: A Comprehensive Survey. *IEEE access* 3, 678–708. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2015.2437951>.
- Jaradat, A.S., Nasayreh, A., Al-Na’amneh, Q., Gharaibeh, H., Al Mamlook, R.E., 2023. Genetic Optimization Techniques for Enhancing Web Attacks Classification in Machine Learning, in: 2023 IEEE Intl Conf on Dependable, Autonomic and Secure Computing, Intl Conf on Pervasive Intelligence and Computing, Intl Conf on Cloud and Big Data Computing, Intl Conf on Cyber Science and Technology Congress (DASC/PiCom/CBDCom/CyberSciTech), pp. 0130–0136. doi:[10.1109/DASC/PiCom/CBDCom/Cy59711.2023.10361399](https://doi.org/10.1109/DASC/PiCom/CBDCom/Cy59711.2023.10361399).
- Kong, J.H., Ang, L.M., Seng, K.P., 2015. A comprehensive survey of modern symmetric cryptographic solutions for resource constrained environments. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications* 49, 15–50. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2014.09.006>.

- Kuliha, M., Verma, S., 2024. Secure internet of medical things based electronic health records scheme in trust decentralized loop federated learning consensus blockchain. *International Journal of Intelligent Networks* 5, 161–174. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijin.2024.03.001>.
- Li, Y., Tian, Y., 2022. A Lightweight and Secure Three-Factor Authentication Protocol With Adaptive Privacy-Preserving Property for Wireless Sensor Networks. *IEEE Systems Journal* 16, 6197–6208. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/JSYST.2022.3152561>.
- Litvinov, E., Llumiguano, H., Santofimia, M.J., del Toro, X., Villanueva, F.J., Rocha, P., 2023. Code Integrity and Confidentiality: An Active Data Approach for Active and Healthy Ageing. *Sensors* 23. doi:10.3390/s23104794.
- López Martínez, A., Gil Pérez, M., Ruiz-Martínez, A., 2023. A Comprehensive Review of the State-of-the-Art on Security and Privacy Issues in Healthcare. *ACM Computing Surveys* 55, 1–38. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/3571156>.
- Ma, E.Y.T., Obimbo, C., 2011. An evolutionary computation attack on one-round TEA. *Procedia Computer Science* 6, 171–176. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2011.08.033>. complex adaptive systems.
- Messinis, S., Temenos, N., Protonotarios, N.E., Rallis, I., Kalogeras, D., Doulamis, N., 2024. Enhancing Internet of Medical Things security with artificial intelligence: A comprehensive review. *Computers in Biology and Medicine* 170, 108036. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2024.108036>.
- Muhammad, G., Alshehri, F., Karray, F., Saddik, A.E., Alsulaiman, M., Falk, T.H., 2021. A comprehensive survey on multimodal medical signals fusion for smart healthcare systems. *Information Fusion* 76, 355–375. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2021.06.007>.
- Neto, E.C.P., Dadkhah, S., Ferreira, R., Zohourian, A., Lu, R., Ghorbani, A.A., 2023a. CICIoT2023: A real-time dataset and benchmark for large-scale attacks in IoT environment. *Sensors* 23, 5941. doi:10.3390/s23135941.

- Neto, E.C.P., Dadkhah, S., Ferreira, R., Zohourian, A., Lu, R., Ghorbani, A.A., 2023b. CICIoT2023: A Real-Time Dataset and Benchmark for Large-Scale Attacks in IoT Environment. *Sensors* 23. doi:[10.3390/s23135941](https://doi.org/10.3390/s23135941).
- Othmane, L.B., Lilien, L., 2009. Protecting privacy of sensitive data dissemination using active bundles, in: 2009 World Congress on Privacy, Security, Trust and the Management of e-Business, IEEE. pp. 202–213. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/CONGRESS.2009.30>.
- Papaioannou, M., Karageorgou, M., Mantas, G., Sucasas, V., Essop, I., Rodriguez, J., Lymberopoulos, D., 2022. A Survey on Security Threats and Countermeasures in Internet of Medical Things (IoMT). *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies* 33, e4049. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/ett.4049>.
- Priyadarshini, R., Panda, M., Mishra, B., 2019. Security in Healthcare Applications based on Fog and Cloud Computing, in: *Cyber Security in Parallel and Distributed Computing: Concepts, Techniques, and Applications*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119488330.ch15>.
- Shrivastava, S., Trung, T.Q., Lee, N.E., 2020. Recent progress, challenges, and prospects of fully integrated mobile and wearable point-of-care testing systems for self-testing. *Chemical Society Reviews* 49, 1812–1866.
- Sowjanya, K., Dasgupta, M., Ray, S., 2021. Elliptic Curve Cryptography based authentication scheme for Internet of Medical Things. *Journal of Information Security and Applications* 58, 102761. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jisa.2021.102761>.
- Sun, W., Cai, Z., Li, Y., Liu, F., Fang, S., Wang, G., 2018. Security and privacy in the medical internet of things: a review. *Security and Communication Networks* 2018, 5978636. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/5978636>.
- Sun, Y., Lo, F.P.W., Lo, B., 2019. Security and Privacy for the Internet of Medical Things Enabled Healthcare Systems: A Survey. *IEEE Access* 7, 183339–183355. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2960617>.

- Sun, Z., An, G., Yang, Y., Liu, Y., 2024. Optimized machine learning enabled intrusion detection 2 system for internet of medical things. *Franklin Open* 6, 100056. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fraope.2023.100056>.
- Sutradhar, S., Majumder, S., Bose, R., Mondal, H., Bhattacharyya, D., 2024. A blockchain privacy-conserving framework for secure medical data transmission in the internet of medical things. *Decision Analytics Journal* 10, 100419. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dajour.2024.100419>.
- Tseng, S.M., Wang, Y.Q., Wang, Y.C., 2024. Multi-Class Intrusion Detection Based on Transformer for IoT Networks Using CIC-IoT-2023 Dataset. *Future Internet* 16. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/1999-5903/16/8/284>, doi:10.3390/fi16080284.
- Turukmane, A.V., Devendiran, R., 2024. M-MultiSVM: An efficient feature selection assisted network intrusion detection system using machine learning. *Computers & Security* 137, 103587. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2023.103587>.
- Villanueva-Miranda, I., Nazeran, H., Martinek, R., 2018. A semantic interoperability approach to heterogeneous internet of medical things (IoMT) platforms, in: 2018 IEEE 20th international conference on e-Health networking, applications and services (HealthCom), IEEE. pp. 1–5. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/HealthCom.2018.8531103>.
- Xu, J., Xue, K., Li, S., Tian, H., Hong, J., Hong, P., Yu, N., 2019. Healthchain: A Blockchain-Based Privacy Preserving Scheme for Large-Scale Health Data. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 6, 8770–8781. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2019.2923525>.
- Zhang, L., Zhu, S., 2015. Robust ECC-based authenticated key agreement scheme with privacy protection for telecare medicine information systems. *Journal of medical systems* 39, 1–11. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10916-015-0233-3>.